
CIM THE APPLICATION OF CITY INFORMATION MODELLING

Everest Çorbaxi

Supervisor

Alessandro Zichi⁽¹⁾

(1) Consorzio CISE Scuola F.Lli Pesenti, P. zza Leonardo da Vinci, 32, Milan, 20132, Italy

Abstract

More than 3.9 billion people now live in urban and suburban areas, accounting for 54% of the global population. This urbanization will continue to grow in the coming years, bringing the population of urban areas to 6 billion by 2045. Urban areas account for 80% of greenhouse gas emissions, 75% waste generation, and 70% global energy consumption.

The growth of urbanization and the rising demand for better efficiency in energy consumption and management of natural resources makes it necessary to deal with building construction and city planning in new and sustainable ways. Information technology progress in 3D city models, Digital Twins, Urban Analytics, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have promoted the recent digital transition.

City Information Modelling entails dealing with enormous amounts of big data, commonly brought together, utilizing cloud computing. CIM provides the integrated management of urban transformation operations and synthesises current paradigmatic references such as sustainability, smartness, and resilience. This thesis presents existing concepts on the Modelling of City Information based on a critical literature review.

The use of technology is indispensable to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of city management, thus enhancing the population's quality of life. Given the above, the urban planners and governors will have to face substantial challenges as to actual and future demands in urban planning, management, and city monitoring.

Dissertation:

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Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/1SrdW4Wyssg>

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